

Seismic data interpolation using a UNet-based machine learning framework with a hybrid loss function

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Abstract

Seismic data acquisition often results in missing traces due to limitations in survey design, equipment failures, or obstructions. To address this, a deep learning-based interpolation framework was developed using a modified UNet architecture optimized with a hybrid loss function combining L1 loss, Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) loss, and Frequency loss. The model was trained on synthetic shot gathers from the BP benchmark dataset, with 50% of traces randomly removed to simulate data with missing traces. The trained model was tested on both synthetic and real seismic gathers to evaluate its interpolation performance. The model performed well on both synthetic and real dataset. Spectral domain analysis, including amplitude and frequency-wavenumber (FK) spectra comparisons, confirmed excellent recovery of both spatial and spectral content. The results emphasize the model's robustness on synthetic data and its limitations on real-field data, underlining the need for incorporating diverse field datasets during training to enhance generality of the model.

Introduction

Seismic data acquisition is often affected by missing traces, arising from various factors such as suboptimal survey design, physical

obstructions within the survey area, equipment malfunctions (dead channels), or intentional data editing. The presence of these gaps in the recorded data requires interpolation techniques, which transforms the irregularly sampled grid into a regularized one, therefore improving subsequent seismic data processing workflows.

A range of methods has been developed to address this problem. One prominent approach is based on wavefield reconstruction, which uses the principle that recorded traces, representing sampled instances of a propagating wavefield, must obey the governing wave equation. Consequently, the complete wavefield including the unrecorded traces can be reconstructed. Another used method involves prediction filter-based methods, which exploit the inherent predictability of seismic events. These approaches typically assume that seismic events exhibit linear or locally linear behavior and can be predicted using neighboring traces. Additionally, several other techniques, such as rank-reduction methods and domain-transformed interpolation methods, have been used. The latter utilize data sparsity in transformed domains to achieve accurate reconstruction.

Recent advancements in deep learning have introduced new possibilities for seismic data interpolation. (Mandelli et al., 2019) demonstrated the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for simultaneous

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Figure 1: The architecture of the proposed interpolation model which is based on UNet architecture.

denoising and interpolation. Furthermore, generative adversarial networks (GANs) have shown promising results in seismic data processing and imaging applications (Kaur et al., 2021).

In the present study, a UNet-based architecture is proposed for interpolating missing traces within seismic gathers. The network optimization was performed using the Adam optimizer. A hybrid loss function comprising three components—L1 loss, Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) loss, and Frequency loss was used. A comprehensive description of these loss functions is provided in the subsequent section. For model training, complete shot gathers with no missing traces were utilized, from which 50% of traces were randomly removed to simulate the occurrence of missing data.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: the subsequent section details the UNet architecture along with the configuration of its hyperparameters. This is followed by an in-depth

explanation of the hybrid loss function. The proposed method is then applied to both synthetic and field datasets to examine its interpolation performance. The paper concludes with a discussion on the factors influencing the generalization capability of the proposed interpolation model.

Methodology

Network Architecture

In this study, a UNet-based architecture (Figure 1) is used for the task of seismic data interpolation. Originally introduced by (Ronneberger et al., 2015) for biomedical image segmentation. The network comprises two primary components: a contracting path (encoder) and an expansive path (decoder). The contracting path adopts the conventional design of a convolutional neural network, consisting of repeated applications of 3×3 convolutional layers, each followed by a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. Downsampling is

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Figure 2: Evolution of Loss metrics over the epochs while training.

achieved through a 2×2 max-pooling operations with a stride of 2. At each downsampling stage, the number of feature channels is doubled, enabling the network to capture progressively abstract and complex features. Conversely, the expansive path reconstructs the output by progressively upsampling the feature maps. Each step within this path involves a 2×2 transposed convolution, which reduces the number of feature channels by half. More importantly, skip connections are incorporated to concatenate feature maps from the corresponding layers in the contracting path with those in the expansive path. This design preserves essential spatial information that might otherwise be lost during downsampling. The concatenated feature maps are then processed through successive 3×3 convolutional layers, each followed by a ReLU activation function.

Original UNet architecture concludes with a 1×1 convolution at the final layer, a modification is introduced in the proposed model by incorporating an additional 3×3 convolutional layer prior to the final output layer. This modification improves the network's capacity to capture localized features and improve the interpolation quality. During the training phase,

the network iteratively updates its learnable parameters by minimizing the predefined loss function, which quantifies the differences between the predicted and true seismic gather.

Model Hyperparameters

A convolutional filter size of 3×3 was selected for this study, suggested by the findings of (Kaur et al., 2020) and supported by prior research indicating that the use of smaller filter sizes generally yields improved network performance (Mahmood et al., 2017). Adam (Adaptive Moment Estimation) is the optimization algorithm used to update the model weights. It uses exponentially decaying averages of past gradients and their squared values to adapt learning rates for each parameter (Kingma & Ba, 2017). For activation function, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) was used. It is one of the simplest and most widely used activation functions in deep learning. ReLU can be defined as:

$$ReLU(x) = \max(0, x).$$

Loss Function

For this study, a hybrid loss function was designed, with a combination of three distinct components: the L1 loss, the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) loss, and the Frequency loss. The idea behind this choice is to leverage the complementary strengths of each loss function in capturing both spatial and spectral characteristics of the seismic data, hence enhancing the overall interpolation performance. The L1 loss, also known as the mean absolute error (MAE), quantifies the average absolute difference between the predicted and true values. In contrast to the L2 loss, which squares the errors and consequently increases the effects of outliers, the L1 loss treats all differences linearly, reducing the impact of extreme values. This property enables the L1 loss to better preserve sharp transitions and edges in the data, as it penalizes both large and small errors equally, thus avoiding over-

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Figure 3: Synthetic Shot 6 with 50% traces removed showing (a) decimated gather, (b) reference (actual) gather, (c) model-interpolated gather, (d) amplitude spectra of (a), (b), and (c), (e) FK spectrum of the actual gather, and (f) FK spectrum of the interpolated gather.

smoothing of important structural details. The mathematical formulation of the L1 loss can be expressed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{L1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i|,$$

where N is the number of data points (pixels in the image), y_i is the true value, and \hat{y}_i is the predicted value.

SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure) is a perceptual metric that measures the similarity between two images based on luminance, contrast, and structure. SSIM Loss can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{SSIM} = 1 - \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)},$$

where μ_x, μ_y are the mean of images of x and y , σ_x^2, σ_y^2 are the variance of x and y , σ_{xy} is the covariance between x and y , and C_1, C_2 are small constants to avoid division by zero. SSIM loss calculated in patches with patch size being 11×11 and then averaging for the entire image.

Frequency loss is computed by comparing the frequency domain representation of predicted and true data. Frequency loss can be defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_F = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N ||F_t(y)_i| - |F_t(\hat{y})_i||,$$

where F_t is the 1D FFT over time and N is the number of frequency components after transformation. The final hybrid loss function, \mathcal{L}_{Total} can be defined as the linear combination

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of all three such that: $\mathcal{L}_{Total} = w_1\mathcal{L}_{L1} + w_2\mathcal{L}_{SSIM} + w_3\mathcal{L}_F$, where w_1, w_2, w_3 are the weightage given to L1 loss, SSIM loss and Frequency loss respectively.

Data Preprocessing

To facilitate training, overlapping patches of size 256×256 were extracted from the shot gathers, with an overlap of 128×128 between adjacent patches. Prior to patch extraction, the input data, specifically, the gathers containing missing traces were subjected to a two-step preprocessing

unit standard deviation. This was followed by normalization, where the data values were linearly scaled to fall within the range of -1 to 1.

Training Dataset

The model was trained using shot gathers from the BP synthetic dataset (Billette & Brandsberg-Dahl, 2005) which is available in public domain and can be accessed from SEG website (SEG, 2004). This dataset was generated through elastic finite-difference modeling applied to a tabular salt velocity model. It features a temporal

Figure 4: Real Shot 7 with 50 % traces removed showing (a) decimated gather, (b) reference (actual) gather, (c) model-interpolated gather, (d) amplitude spectra of (a), (b), and (c), (e) FK spectrum of the actual gather, and (f) FK spectrum of the interpolated gather.

procedure involving standardization and normalization. In the standardization step, each gather was rescaled to achieve a zero mean and

sampling interval of 0.006 second, with a 50 m shot spacing and a 12.5 m receiver group interval. The inclusion of a water layer and complex salt

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bodies within the velocity model introduces multiple reflections and intricate move-out patterns. The presence of these geological features results in complex seismic wave propagation behavior, making this dataset particularly challenging and suitable for evaluating the performance of interpolation algorithms (Crawley et al., 2005). The model was trained on a total of 102,492 samples, each with dimensions of 256×256 , over the course of 200 epochs. The training was performed using NVIDIA Quadro 6000 GPU, with each epoch requiring approximately two hours to complete. A batch size of 16 was used during training to balance memory constraints with optimization efficiency. The modified UNet architecture was implemented using the PyTorch deep learning framework within the Python programming environment. The evolution of the loss values during training is illustrated in Figure 2, depicting the progression of the total loss, L1 loss,

and Frequency loss components across successive epochs.

Performance Metric

To evaluate the performance of the model, two metrics are used: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the signal reconstruction percentage (SRP). R^2 is a statistical measure indicating the closeness between two variables and is defined as: $\mathcal{R}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y^i - \hat{y}^i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y^i - \bar{y})^2}$, where y^i and \hat{y}^i represent the original and predicted samples obtained using the proposed model, respectively. \bar{y} is the mean of the original samples, and N is the number of samples. To quantify the percentage of signal recovered by the model, the SRP metric is defined as:

$$SRP = 100 * \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_T} (y^i - \hat{y}^i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_T} (y^i)^2} \right),$$

where N_T is the number of traces.

Figure 5: Scatter plots comparing original and predicted shot gathers. The x-axis represents the original shot gather values, while the y-axis shows the corresponding predicted values. (a) depicts results for synthetic Shot 6 with 50% traces removed, and (b) presents results for real Shot 7 with 50% traces removed

Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) loss,

Results and Discussion

The interpolation performance of the proposed method was evaluated by removing 40%, 50%, and 60% of traces from seven shot gathers, comprising six from the synthetic dataset (Shot 1 to Shot 6) and one from the Mahanadi 2D seismic dataset (Shot 7). Reconstruction accuracy was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and Signal Reconstruction Percentage (SRP), with the results summarized in Table 1. Across the six synthetic shot gathers, the model consistently demonstrated high reconstruction accuracy for all levels of trace removal. At 40% removal, R^2 values exceeded 0.98 for all synthetic shots, with Shot 6 achieving a peak value of 0.99 with signal recovery of more than 99%. Even at 60% trace removal, the model maintained strong performance, preserving R^2 values above 0.95 and SRP values exceeding 94% in most cases. These outcomes affirm the model's robustness in

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managing significant data sparsity under controlled, noise-free conditions. To further evaluate the model’s effectiveness, a spectral domain analysis was conducted by comparing the frequency spectra of the predicted and reference gathers in both the frequency and frequency–wavenumber (FK) domains, as illustrated in Figure 3. For the synthetic data, a close match was observed between the predicted and original spectra, confirming the model’s ability to reconstruct both the spatial and spectral content of seismic gathers.

For Shot 7, corresponding to a real shot gather from the Mahanadi 2D seismic survey, comparatively lower but encouraging reconstruction accuracy was achieved. At 40% trace removal, R^2 reached 0.79, with values of 0.7 and 0.62 at 50% and 60% removal, respectively, and SRP values of 78.11%, 67.89%, and 58.63% respectively. Spectral domain analysis of the real dataset, involving amplitude and FK spectrum comparisons as shown in Figure 4, demonstrated that the predicted gathers effectively recovered the dominant spectral content. While subtle variations in amplitude and FK spectra were present, the overall reconstruction preserved the primary structural and spectral features of the original data, particularly in the presence of coherent noise. A scatter plot comparison of original and predicted gathers for Shot 6 (synthetic) and Shot 7 (real), provided in Figure 5, further illustrates the model’s interpolation accuracy across both synthetic and field datasets. These findings confirm the model’s usability for practical seismic data interpolation applications and highlight the potential for performance improvement through the inclusion of broader, field-representative training datasets.

Conclusion

This study tested a machine learning based interpolation method using modified UNet on both synthetic and real seismic gathers. The

method showed excellent results on synthetic and real seismic data, successfully reconstructing missing traces with high accuracy. When applied to field data from the Mahanadi 2D seismic survey, the model performed well but showed some challenges due to noise. Spectral analyses confirmed strong spatial and spectral reconstruction in synthetic cases and encouraging results in field data. These findings highlight the method’s potential for practical use in seismic data processing. Since the model was trained only on synthetic data, future work will focus on including diverse field data in training and refining the model’s ability to handle field noise and geological complexity, aiming for even better performance.

Table 1: Results for seven shot gathers with varying combinations of removed traces.

Traces Removed	40%		50%		60%		
	Shot	R^2	SRP	R^2	SRP	R^2	SRP
1		0.99	98.94	0.98	98.32	0.98	97.52
2		0.98	98.38	0.97	97.40	0.95	94.85
3		0.98	98.45	0.97	97.46	0.95	95.00
4		0.99	98.74	0.98	97.63	0.96	96.34
5		0.99	98.90	0.98	97.90	0.97	96.94
6		0.99	99.13	0.99	98.51	0.97	97.19
7		0.79	78.11	0.70	67.89	0.62	58.63

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